

Wearable device for monitoring fetal and maternal health dursing pregnancy

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Abstract:

Wearable devices for monitoring fetal and maternal health, like AI-powered smart belts, provide continuous, real-time, remote tracking of heart rates, uterine contractions, and movements. These devices, often utilizing sensors such as Doppler ultrasound, electrocardiography, and accelerometers, enhance maternal and fetal safety by allowing clinicians to remotely monitor high-risk pregnancies and intervene early when deviations from normal physiology are detected. This article presents a comprehensive design patent-oriented discussion of a wearable device intended for continuous monitoring of fetal and maternal health during pregnancy, focusing on design rationale, system architecture, sensor integration, safety considerations, and clinical applications, while highlighting innovation and patentability within the context of recent technological advances in prenatal care.

Keywords:

Wearable devices, fetal monitoring, maternal health, pregnancy, smart belt, design patent, remote monitoring, prenatal care.
